

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**CLINICAL VERIFICATION OF VERIFIED YET IGNORED
SYMPTOMS OF COCHLEARIA ARMORACIA FROM
HERING'S GUIDING SYMPTOMS - A PILOT STUDY****Anit Acharya* and Prof. Tarkeshwar Jain**Assistant Professor*, Department of Materia Medica, Homoeopathy University, Jaipur.
Head of Department of Materia Medica, Homoeopathy University, Jaipur.**Abstract:**

Constantine Hering's priceless work the "The Guiding Symptoms Of Our Materia Medica" is known to be a matured form of Materia Medica. In his work, he evaluated the symptoms, which is considered as the practical advancement in the field of Materia Medica. The authenticity of this book greatly influenced many authors of Materia Medicas, who acknowledged their gratitude to Hering's work in the prefaces of their own work, but they overlooked many of the first and second grade symptoms of medicines which were verified and repeatedly verified by cures. Considering this lacunae a need was felt to clinically verify the ignored first and second grade symptoms as given in Hering's Guiding Symptoms and to compile them. Hering in his first two volume of the the Guiding Symptoms of Materia Medica justified his work, but after his demise his work was ignored in later volumes. Thus a pilot study was undertaken to verify the ignored symptoms of Cochlearia armoracia. The study was an open label clinical trial conducted at the OPD/IPDs of Dr. Madan Pratap Khunteta Homoeopathic Medical College, Hospital & Research Centre, Jaipur, for a period of 6 months, for which 30 Cases were randomly selected and were prescribed Cochlearia armoracia based on the symptoms similarity.

In this study 07 symptoms out of 22 ignored symptoms of Cochleria armoracia were considered for the clinical verification. It was observed that the medicine relieved Toothache of rheumatic character (20%), Rheumatism, wandering, chronic (33.3%). Marked improvement with 75% was seen each in cramps after cold, backache and in mucous stools. Cochlearia armoracia showed (60%) improvement each in female complaints like leucorrhoea and in headache since climaxis.

Keywords: *Clinical verification, Cochlearia armoracia, The Guiding Symptoms Of Our Materia Medica.*

Corresponding author:**Anit Acharya,**

Homoeopathy University,

Saipura, Sanganer, Jaipur.

E-mail: anitsingh.vikram@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Anit Acharya et al., *Clinical Verification of Verified Yet Ignored Symptoms of Cochlearia Armoracia from Hering's Guiding Symptoms - a Pilot Study*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(06).

INTRODUCTION:

Evidence-based Homoeopathy is the need of the hour as many stalwarts all over the globe accept it as a proof of clinical efficacy of Homoeopathic Medicine. Clinical verification is one of the criterion to justify the evidence based medicine. This is a classical method to determine the pathogenetic power of homoeopathic medicines in order to evolve a reliable Materia Medica [1].

Constantine Hering is widely known as "The Father of American Homeopathy" His masterpiece "The Guiding Symptoms of our Materia Medica.", is said as "When a traveller loses his way he comes to a guide board, with a hand pointing or guiding the right way, – so it shall be 'Guiding Symptoms.'" His life-long experiences of fifty years were compiled by him in ten volumes out of which he successfully penned in first two volumes but unfortunately failed to complete his unsurmountable task that was later completed by Calvin B. Knerr, Charles G. Raue and Charles Mohr. Though the later work lacked in authenticity it still stood as the Magnum Opus of Homoeopathy. The name "Guiding Symptoms" was chosen after much thought and discussion as he said to his students, "I want to make it the shortest way to selecting a remedy." [2].

Since the book is referred as best reference book [3-8], it requires meticulous experiments for the validation of the clinically verified symptoms. For the study *Cochlearia armoracia* was chosen, from Hering's Guiding Symptoms for clinical verification. The medicine selected was not well represented in other Materia Medicas that were influenced by this great piece of work. As conscientious homeopaths, we owe it to our patients, and our profession, that we strive constantly to follow the footsteps [9].

About the plant

Botanical Name - *Cochlearia armoracia* Linn.

Synonyms. —

Latin: *Armoracia rusticana* Gaertn, *Armoracia Laphathifolia* Gilib, *A. sativa*, *Cochlearia rusticana*, *Nasturtium amphibium*, *N. armoracia*, *Raphanus rusticanus*, *Roripa rusticana*, *Sisymbrium amphibium*, *S. indicum*;

English: Amphibious cress, Horse radish. Scurvy grass. Water cress. Water radish;

French: Radis de cheval, Moustarde des moines;

German: Meerrettig.

Natural Order — Cruciferae (Brassicaceae)

Description — A perennial, herbaceous plant, with fusiform root large, long, scarred, nearly smooth, with thick, horizontal branches, brownish-yellow externally, whitish internally, very pungent and acrid when broken. The stems are erect, 2 or 3 feet high, branched at the top. The leaves are alternate;

the radical leaves are very large, oblong, crenate, rarely pinnatifid; the stem leaves are lanceolate. The flowers are cruciform, corolla white, petals 6-8mm long, pedicels after anthesis ascending, 8-12 mm long, white in terminal racemes and appear in May and June. Fruit obovoid, 2celled upto 6mm long but usually falling early; style about 0.3 mm long, with broad persistent stigma [10,11].

Habitat — A native of Russia. Found throughout the United States and Canada in moist grounds, escaped from cultivation. To a small extent in gardens both in Northern India and the hills of Southern India [12]

History — Named derived from cochlear, a spoon; from the shape of the leaves. During the middle-ages the root and leaves were used as a medicine and as condiment. Introduced into homoeopathic practice in 1838 by Dr. Franz [13].

Part Used— The fresh root.

Macroscopy: Tap root upto 30 cm in length and upto 3.5 to 5 cm in thickness, light yellow brownish, internally white and fleshy, fracture of dried root short, taste somewhat sweet, pungent and acrid; odour pungent upon bruising [12].

PHARMACOLOGY:

Constituents: One of the most researched constituents of horse-radish is horse-radish peroxidase. Other horse-radish constituents include glucosinolates (sinigrin, glucobrassicin, neoglucobrassicin, and gluconasturtiin), myrosinase, plastoquinone-9, 6-O-acyl-beta-d-glucosyl-beta-sitosterol, 1,2-dilinenoyl-3-galactosylglycerol, 3-acyl-sitosterols, and phosphatidylcholines. When horse-radish cells are damaged by cutting, grating, or chewing, enzymes convert sinigrin to allyl isothiocyanate (mustard oil) [14].

Several studies have been carried to find its pharmacologic abilities.

- **Antibacterial activity:** In a prospective cohort study conducted by Goos et al., patients (age of four years or older) with acute sinusitis, bronchitis, or urinary tract infections (UTI) treated with Angocin Anti-Infekt N (nasturtium herb and horseradish root) had similar decreases in symptom severity as the control patients taking standard antibiotic therapy [15].
- **Anticancer activity:** In two similar *in vitro* studies by the same authors, 1,2-dilinenoyl-3-galactosylglycerol isolated from horseradish rhizomes dose-dependently inhibited the proliferation of colon cancer cells (HCT-116) and lung cancer cells (NCI-H460); 9An early animal study also supports these anticancer findings [16].

- **Anticoagulant/antiplatelet activity:** In an animal study using intravenous horseradish peroxidase, the authors concluded that intravenous horseradish peroxidase stimulated synthesis of arachidonic acid metabolites [17].
- **Antihypertensive activity:** In animal studies, horseradish has caused hypotension [18].
- **Anti-inflammatory activity:** In *in vitro* study using isolates from horseradish, 60mcg/mL of plastoquinone-9 and 6-O-acyl-beta-d-glucosyl-beta-sitosterol selectively inhibited COX-1 enzyme by 28 and 32%, respectively [19].
- **Antimutagenic activity:** In an *in vitro* study, horseradish has shown antimutagenic activity [20].
- **Antithyroid activity:** In an *in vitro* study, horseradish peroxidase combined with H₂O₂ formed stable compounds that catalyzed both iodination and thyroid hormone formation [21].

Cochlearia armoracia

Ignored first and second grade symptoms from Hering Guiding Symptoms

Mind

- | Difficult thinking in evening.
- | Melancholy is changed into merry mood.
- | Anxiety. ⊖ Hydrothorax.
- | Driven to despair. ⊖ Cramp in stomach
- | Worse from nervous excitement; from vexation.

Smell and nose

- | Inflammation of nose. ⊖ with eye complaints.

Teeth and gums

- | Toothache, especially of a rheumatic character.
- | Scorbutis.
- | Toothache in carious teeth. ⊖ Scurvy.

Taste and tongue

- | Glossoplegia.
- | Tongue furred whitish. ⊖ Cramp in stomach.

Throat

- | Dryness of pharynx, larynx and posterior nares.
- | Warm water put in mouth seemed to go no further than throat. ⊖ Apparent death.

Stool and rectum

- | Mucous stools.
- | Intestinal catarrh
- | Itching and burning at anus.

Urinary organs

- | Increased secretion of urine.
- | Nephritis albuminosa, with great paleness, and atony of kidneys.

Male sexual organs

- | Impotence, torpidity.

Inflammatory stage of gonorrhoea.

Gonorrhoea, with violent smarting and burning, difficult micturition, and a rather scanty discharge from urethra.

Gonorrhoea, after cutting and burning pains during micturition had been nearly removed by 1st or 2d dilution, the 6th acted with good effect.

Chronic and neglected gonorrhoea.

Female sexual organs

Leucorrhoea and menostasis.

Since climaxis, cramp in stomach.

Voice and larynx

Loss of voice; whispering.

Aphonia, with blood-spitting.

Hoarseness and roughness in throat

Heart, pulse and circulation

No pulsation of heart; apparent death.

Pulse small. Θ Cramp in stomach.

Neck and back

A slight pressure on last dorsal vertebra increases pain exceedingly. Θ Cramp in stomach.

Lower limbs

Suppressed foot sweats.

Tissues

Rheumatism, wandering, chronic.

Antiscorbutic.

Dropsy, with albuminuria.

After pneumonia, during convalescence.

Beginning enteritis.

Stages of life, constitution

A woman suffering from violent headache, with vomiting, since climaxis. Θ Cramp in stomach.¹³

METHODOLOGY:

The participants for the study were drawn from the OPD/IPD of Dr. Madan Pratap Khunteta Homoeopathic Medical College, Hospital & Research Centre, Jaipur. Their presenting signs and symptoms were recorded in the predefined case recording proforma. In 30 cases Cochlearia armoracea was prescribed for a period of 6 months based on the symptoms similarity. The medicine was procured from a GMP certified pharmacy. If there was no change in the symptoms and the signs for a significant period, next higher potencies like 200 and 1M were prescribed, and in case of no

change was observed, even after change of potencies, the case was dropped.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

The data of all the cases were collected, compiled and analysed. Table 01 shows the clinically verified symptoms on the basis of the number of patients who got relieved along with the available symptoms. In the column 'improvement observed' the numerator denotes the number of patients who got relieved after the prescribed medicine, and the denominator denotes the total number of patient to whom the medicine was prescribed.

TABLE 01

Location	Symptoms	Improvement Observed (% in within brackets)
Tooth and gums	┃ Toothache of rheumatic character	1/5 (20%)
Stool and rectum	┃ Mucous stools.	3/4 (75%)
Female sexual organs	┃ Leucorrhoea and menostasis	3/5 (60%)
Neck and back	┃ A slight pressure on last dorsal vertebra increases pain exceedingly. ⊖ Cramp in stomach.	3/4 (75%)
Tissues	┃ Rheumatism, wandering, chronic.	1/3 (33.3%)
Stages of life, constitution	┃ A woman suffering from violent headache, with vomiting, since climaxis. ⊖ Cramp in stomach	3/5(60%)
Stomach	┃ After a cold: cramp in stomach.	3/4 (75%)

The study verified the ignored first and second grade of symptoms of *Cochlearia armoracia* as given in Hering's Guiding symptoms. *Cochlearia armoracia* widely prescribed by clinicians for urinary tract infections are also being locally given for removing dandruff(13).But with this study it was observed that other than these symptoms the medicine relieved Toothache of rheumatic character(20%), Rheumatism, wandering, chronic(33.3%).Marked improvement with 75% each was seen in Cramps after cold,Backache and in Mucous stools .*Cochlearia armoracia* showed (60%) improvement each in Female complaints

like Leucorrhoea and in Headache since climaxis.These verified symptoms can be compiled to form a comprehensive Materia Medica with the repertory for the easy use of the clinicians.This study also showed *Cochlearia armoracia* showing better results in Chronic complaints 18cases(60%) than in Acute complaints 12 cases(40%). The small sample size and variability in selected population samples limits the statistical significance of this study. Thus suggesting that more of such studies should be conducted with larger sample size and specific disease condition to increase the effectiveness of this study

(FIGURE 01: The graph showing the distribution of cases according to the classification of the symptoms in Cochlearia armoracia)

REPERTORY

A concise repertory of the verified symptoms of Cochlearia armoracia has been compiled based on the Repertory of the Homoeopathic Materia Medica by J T Kent for the purpose of quick reference.

TEETH

PAIN

Rheumatic

STOMACH

PAIN, cramping

Cold drinks, after

Cold, from a

STOOL

MUCOUS

Slimy

GENTALIA – FEMALE

LEUCORRHOEA

BACK

DORSAL REGION

EXTREMITIES

RHEUMATIC

WANDERING SHIFTING

HEAD

PAIN

Violent pains

Vomiting

Climaxis, during the

CONCLUSION:

The study reveals the ignored symptoms of *Cochlearia armoracia* as given in Hering's Guiding Symptoms by verifying the symptoms. Further clinical trials with suitable study designs are required to validate such conditions and to enhance the usefulness of the medicines.

REFERENCES:

1. Chakraborty P, et al. Cassia fistula - A multicentric clinical verification study. CCRH IJRH [Internet]. 2011; Vol 5, No. 2(cited on 7 July 2017) Available from: <http://ccrhindia.org/ijrh/5%282%29/4.pdf>
2. Navab I. History of Homeopathy – Constantine Hering. HpathyEzine [Internet]. 2012 [cited 7 July 2017]; Available from: <http://hpathy.com/history-of-medicine/history-of-homeopathy-constantine-hering/>
3. Clarke J. A dictionary of practical Materia Medica. New Delhi, India: B. Jain Publishers; 1990. Sec. Preface, the schema: Page No.4-5.
4. Kent J. Lectures on homoeopathic Materia Medica. New Delhi, India: B. Jain Publishers; 2007. Preface to 1st edition: Page No.11.
5. Burt W. Characteristic Materia Medica. New Delhi, India: B. Jain Publishers; 1997. Preface to 1st edition: Page No.6.
6. Hughes R. A manual of pharmacodynamics. New Delhi, India: B. Jain Publishers; 1983. Preface to 6th edition; Sec. Introductory: Page No.6.
7. Farrington E. A clinical Materia Medica. New Delhi, India: B. Jain Publishers; 2003. 1st edition Sec. Memorium Page No.13-14.
8. Boericke W. Pocket manual of homoeopathic Materia Medica; 1927. Preface to 9th edition: Page No.7-8; Available from: <http://www.homeoint.org/books/boericmm/preface.html>
9. Hering C. The guiding symptoms of our Materia Medica. New Delhi, India: B. Jain Publishers; 1991. Sec. Introduction by Dr. Jugal Kishore: Page No.3.
10. Homoeopathic pharmacopoeia of India vol 3; e book 2016 augmented and revised edition, pg 733-734
11. Horse Radish. Homoeopathic pharmacopoeia of America (cited on 07 July 2017) available on https://archive.org/stream/homoeopathicpha00phargoog/homoeopathicpha00phargoog_djvu.txtCCXMLEARIA ARMORAOA.
12. Standardisation of homoeopathic drugs; vol 3; published CCRH-New Delhi 200; pg 50-53
13. Hering C. The guiding symptoms of our Materia Medica. New Delhi, India: B. Jain Publishers; 1991.pg 542-49.
14. Horseradish (*Armoracia rusticana*) cited on 07 July 2017 available on <http://www.sigmaaldrich.com/life-science/nutrition-research/learning-center/plant-profiler/armoracia-rusticana.html>
15. Goos, K. H., Albrecht, U., and Schneider, B. [Efficacy and safety profile of a herbal drug containing nasturtium herb and horseradish root in acute sinusitis, acute bronchitis and acute urinary tract infection in comparison with other treatments in the daily practice/results of a prospective cohort study]. *Arzneimittel forschung* 2006;56(3):249-257.
16.) Weil, M. J., Zhang, Y., and Nair, M. G. Tumor cell proliferation and cyclooxygenase inhibitory constituents in horseradish (*Armoracia rusticana*) and Wasabi (*Wasabia japonica*). *J Agric Food Chem* 3-9-2005;53(5):1440-1444. 15740020
17. Sjaastad, O. V., Blom, A. K., and Haye, R. Hypotensive effects in cats caused by horseradish peroxidase mediated by metabolites of arachidonic acid. *J Histochem. Cytochem.* 1984;32(12):1328-1330
18. Deimann, W., Taugner, R., and Fahimi, H. D. Arterial hypotension induced by horseradish peroxidase in various rat strains. *J Histochem Cytochem* 1976;24(12):1213-1217
19. Weil, M. J., Zhang, Y., and Nair, M. G. Tumor cell proliferation and cyclooxygenase inhibitory constituents in horseradish (*Armoracia rusticana*) and Wasabi (*Wasabia japonica*). *J Agric Food Chem* 3-9-2005;53(5):1440-1444
20. Kinae, N., Masuda, H., Shin, Il S., Furugori, M., and Shimoi, K. Functional properties of wasabi and horseradish. *Biofactors* 2000;13(1-4):265-269.
21. Deme, D., Virion, A., Michot, J. L., and Pommier, J. Thyroid hormone synthesis and thyroglobulin iodination related to the peroxidase localization of oxidizing equivalents: studies with cytochrome c peroxidase and horseradish peroxidase. *Arch Biochem Biophys* 2-1-1985;236(2):559-566.